

The Prospects of Nanotechnology in Food Processing

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Abstract

The convergence of nanotechnology and food safety represents a frontier of scientific innovation with transformative potential. This paper explores the integration of nanotechnology into the field of food safety, focusing on advancements that have significant implications for food manufacturing, processing, and packaging. At the heart of this intersection is the manipulation of materials at the nano-scale, particularly the incorporation of nano-particles with antimicrobial properties into food packaging materials. Silver and copper nano-particles, in particular, have exhibited remarkable antimicrobial effects, actively resisting the growth of pathogens and thereby extending the shelf life of food products. As consumer concerns about food quality and health benefits rise, the demand for nano-particle-based materials in the food industry has surged due to their stability at high temperatures, proven non-toxicity, and diverse applications in additives, nutrient delivery, and packaging enhancement. This paper categorizes nanotechnology applications in the food sector into two main groups: food nano-structured ingredients and food nano-sensing. The former includes additives, nutrient carriers, anti-caking agents, antimicrobial agents, and packaging material improvement, while the latter is employed for quality and safety evaluation.

Keywords: Nanotechnology, food safety, nanoparticles, antimicrobial properties, food packaging,

Introduction

Nanotechnology refers to the understanding and control of matter at a nanoscale where unique phenomena enable novel applications. Nanomaterials are further defined as substances between 1 and 100 nm in size showing physical, chemical and biological properties that are not found in bulk samples of the same material. Their extremely small size and high surface area are associated with their greater strength, stability and chemical and biological activities. Therefore, nanotechnology enables development of novel materials with a wide range of potential applications. Nanomaterials are used in a variety of consumer, medical, commercial and industrial products. Because nanotechnology is an emerging, rapidly developing technology, very limited information about it is currently available

The intersection of nano-technology and food safety is a field characterized by cutting-edge advancements and transformative potential. Nanotechnology involves manipulating materials at the nano-scale, typically at dimensions less than 100 nano-meters. At this scale, materials exhibit unique properties that can be harnessed for various applications, including those aimed at addressing food-borne pathogens. One key application is the integration of nano-particles with antimicrobial properties into food packaging materials. Silver and copper nano-particles, for instance, have demonstrated

potent antimicrobial effects against a broad spectrum of pathogens. When incorporated into packaging, these nano-particles create surfaces that actively resist the growth of bacteria, viruses, and fungi, thereby extending the shelf life of food products and reducing the risk of contamination during storage and transportation.

Increasing consumer concerns regarding food quality and health benefits have driven researchers to explore ways to enhance food quality without compromising nutritional value. The demand for nano-particle-based materials in the food industry has surged due to their inclusion of essential elements and proven non-toxicity (Roselli et al., 2003). These materials demonstrate stability at high temperatures and pressures, making them suitable for various food applications (Sawai, 2003). Nano-technology provides comprehensive solutions in food manufacturing, processing, and packaging, influencing not only food quality and safety but also the health benefits derived from food. Researchers, organizations, and industries are actively developing novel techniques, methods, and products with direct applications of nanotechnology in food science (Dasgupta et al., 2015).

Nano-technology's applications in the food sector can be broadly categorized into two main groups: food nano-structured ingredients and food nano-sensing. Food nano-structured ingredients encompass a wide range, from acting as food additives and carriers for nutrient delivery to serving as anti-caking agents, antimicrobial agents, and fillers for packaging material improvement. On the other hand, food nano-sensing is employed to enhance food quality and safety evaluation (Ezhilarasi et al., 2013).

Nanotechnology in Food Processing:

Nano-structured food ingredients are developed with claims of offering improved taste, texture, and consistency (Cientifica Report, 2006). Nanotechnology contributes to increasing the shelf life of various food materials and reducing food wastage due to microbial infestation (Pradhan et al., 2015). Nano-carriers are now utilized as delivery systems for food additives without altering the fundamental morphology of the products. Particle size plays a crucial role in the efficient absorption of bioactive compounds, with submicron nano-particles proving more effective than larger micro-particles in certain cell lines (Ezhilarasi et al., 2013). Ideal delivery systems need to deliver active compounds precisely to the target place, ensure availability at a specific rate and time, and efficiently maintain active compounds over extended periods (during storage). Nanotechnology, through the creation of encapsulation, emulsions, biopolymer matrices, simple solutions, and association colloids, provides efficient delivery systems meeting these criteria. Nano polymers are emerging as replacements for conventional materials in food packaging, while nano-sensors prove valuable in detecting contaminants, mycotoxins, and microorganisms in food (Bratovčič, 2015).

Nano-particles offer superior encapsulation and release efficiency compared to traditional systems. Nano-encapsulations mask odours or tastes, control interactions of active ingredients with the food matrix, regulate the release of active agents, and protect them from moisture, heat, chemical, or biological degradation during processing, storage, and utilization. Moreover, these delivery systems,

due to their smaller size, can penetrate tissues deeply, enabling efficient delivery of active compounds to target sites in the body (Lamprecht et al., 2004). Various synthetic and natural polymer-based encapsulating delivery systems have been developed to improve the bioavailability and preservation of active food components. The significance of nano-technology in food processing becomes evident when considering its role in enhancing food products in terms of texture, appearance, taste, nutritional value, and shelf life. Nanotechnology has not only touched upon all these aspects but has also brought about significant alterations in food products, providing them with novel qualities.

Texture, Taste, and Appearance Enhancement in Food through Nanotechnology

Nanotechnology offers diverse solutions for enhancing food quality, particularly in improving taste, texture, and appearance. A widely utilized approach involves the broad application of nano-encapsulation techniques, contributing to enhanced flavour release and retention while achieving culinary balance (Nakagawa, 2014). Zhang et al. (2014) demonstrated the effectiveness of nano-encapsulation in preserving the highly reactive and unstable plant pigment anthocyanins, known for their diverse biological activities. The encapsulation of cyanidin-3-O-glucoside (C3G) molecules within the inner cavity of recombinant soybean seed H-2 subunit ferritin (rH-2) not only improved thermal stability but also enhanced photostability. This innovative design and fabrication of multifunctional nanocarriers aimed at protecting and delivering bioactive molecules.

Rutin, a common dietary flavonoid with significant pharmacological activities, faces limitations in the food industry due to poor solubility. Ferritin nanocages encapsulation proved beneficial in enhancing the solubility, thermal stability, and UV radiation resistance of rutin compared to its free form (Yang et al., 2015). The utilization of nano-emulsions for delivering lipid-soluble bioactive compounds is gaining popularity, given their ability to be produced using natural food ingredients through straightforward production methods. Furthermore, nanoemulsions can be designed to enhance water dispersion and bioavailability (Ozturk et al., 2015).

In comparison to larger particles, which generally release encapsulated compounds more slowly over extended periods, nanoparticles present a promising avenue for improving the bioavailability of nutraceutical compounds. Metallic oxides such as titanium dioxide and silicon dioxide (SiO₂), conventionally used as colour or flow agents in food items, have found application in nanotechnology (Ottaway, 2010). SiO₂ nanomaterials, in particular, are extensively employed as carriers for fragrances or flavours in various food products (Dekkers et al., 2011).

Preservation or Prolonging Shelf-Life:

In the realm of functional foods, where bioactive components are susceptible to degradation, leading to eventual inactivation in harsh environments, the application of nano-encapsulation proves instrumental in extending the shelf-life of food products. This technique effectively slows down degradation processes or prevents them until the product reaches its intended destination. Additionally, the incorporation of edible nano-coatings on various food materials acts as a barrier to moisture and

gas exchange. These coatings not only deliver colours, flavours, antioxidants, enzymes, and anti-browning agents but also contribute to the increased shelf life of manufactured foods, even after the packaging is opened (Renton, 2006; Weiss et al., 2006). By encapsulating functional components within droplets, chemical degradation processes can be deliberately decelerated by engineering the properties of the interfacial layer surrounding them. For instance, curcumin, the most active yet least stable bioactive component of turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), exhibited reduced antioxidant activity and enhanced stability to pasteurization and varying ionic strength upon encapsulation (Sari et al., 2015).

Nanotechnology in Food Packaging

An ideal packaging material should possess both gas and moisture permeability, coupled with strength and biodegradability (Couch et al., 2016). Nanobased "smart" and "active" food packagings offer numerous advantages over conventional methods, providing superior packaging materials with enhanced mechanical strength, barrier properties, antimicrobial films, and incorporating nano-sensing for pathogen detection, thereby alerting consumers to the safety status of food (Mihindukulasuriya and Lim, 2014). The application of nanocomposites as an active material for packaging and material coating proves valuable in improving food packaging (Pinto et al., 2013). Researchers have shown interest in studying the antimicrobial properties of organic compounds like essential oils, organic acids, and bacteriocins (Gálvez et al., 2007; Schirmer et al., 2009), incorporating them into polymeric matrices as antimicrobial packaging. However, these organic compounds face challenges in high-temperature and high-pressure food processing steps due to their sensitivity to such conditions. In contrast, inorganic nano-particles offer a strong antibacterial activity even in low concentrations and exhibit enhanced stability under extreme conditions.

Conclusion

The convergence of nanotechnology and food safety presents groundbreaking advancements with transformative potential. Nano-particles, especially antimicrobial ones like silver and copper, integrated into food packaging materials exhibit potent effects against pathogens, extending shelf life and reducing contamination risks. Rising consumer concerns about food quality and health benefits drive the demand for nano-particle-based materials, renowned for stability at high temperatures and pressures. Nanotechnology's impact spans food manufacturing, processing, and packaging, influencing quality, safety, and health benefits. Two main categories include food nano-structured ingredients and food nano-sensing, playing diverse roles in additives, nutrient delivery, antimicrobial agents, and packaging enhancement.

In food processing, nano-structured ingredients promise improved taste, texture, and shelf life. Nano-carriers efficiently deliver food additives without altering product morphology. Nano-particles provide superior encapsulation, preserving active agents during processing, storage, and utilization. Nanotechnology significantly enhances various aspects of food products, including texture, appearance, taste, nutritional value, and shelf life. Techniques like nano-encapsulation contribute to

enhanced flavour release, preservation of plant pigments, and improved solubility in flavonoids. Nano-emulsions gain popularity for delivering lipid-soluble bioactive compounds. In functional foods, nano-encapsulation extends shelf life by slowing degradation processes, and edible nano-coatings act as barriers, delivering components while increasing shelf life. The deliberate deceleration of chemical degradation processes is exemplified by curcumin's enhanced stability. Nanotechnology in food packaging introduces "smart" and "active" materials with superior mechanical strength, barrier properties, antimicrobial films, and nano-sensing for pathogen detection. The integration of nanotechnology and food safety offers transformative solutions, revolutionizing food production, quality, and safety for consumer and industry benefits.

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